

HELPDESK RESPONSE

Special Educational Needs and Disabilities in Ghana: A Landscape Analysis

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABA	Applied Behaviour Analysis
ADHD	Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder
ECE	Early Childhood Education
ECCD	Early Childhood Care and Development
ESP	Education Strategic Plan
GES	Ghana Education Service
GGA	Good Governance Africa
GNAD	Ghana National Association of the Deaf
IDD	Intellectual and Developmental Disability
IEMT	Inclusive Education Monitoring Tool
JHS	Junior High Schools
KG	Kindergarten
KII	Key Informant Interviews
MMDA	Metropolitan, Municipal, and District Assemblies
MoE	Ministry of Education
MoGCSP	Ministry of Gender, Children and Social Protection
NAC	National Assessment Centre
NaCCA	National Council for Curriculum and Assessment
NCPD	National Council on Persons with Disability
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
PWDs	Persons with Disabilities
SEND	Special educational needs and disabilities
SHS	Senior High School
T-TEL	Transforming Teacher Education and Learning Initiative

Executive summary

Globally, it is estimated that about 150 million children are living with disabilities ([↑Adjei et al., 2025](#)). In Ghana, the 2021 census results showed that approximately 219,022 children aged 5–15 have a disability, and approximately 16% of these children have never attended school ([↑Ghana Statistical Service, 2023](#)). However, limited evidence is available regarding how special educational needs and disabilities (SEND) are addressed in both policy and practice in Ghana.

This landscape analysis provides an overview of the current status of SEND in Ghana. The study adopted a two-phase sequential design:

- A desk review of available evidence providing a comprehensive overview of policy, service delivery systems, infrastructure and resource availability, socio-cultural dynamics, and teacher capacity on SEND in Ghana.
- Empirical research investigating perspectives and experiences of key stakeholders with regard to SEND.

The desk review findings show that although policies and frameworks supporting inclusive education are in place, significant challenges and barriers to the effective inclusion of learners with SEND persist. These include persistent stigma and negative attitudes towards SEND, infrastructural and socio-economic barriers, inadequate teacher training and continuous professional development opportunities, limited access to EdTech, and insufficient and inconsistent financing to support the implementation of inclusive education policies. Further, the desk review outlines the following gaps:

- Limited data and evidence regarding SEND conceptualisation, perspectives and experiences in the country.
- Evidence on the effectiveness of SEND initiatives remains limited.
- Comprehensive data on learners with SEND—including enrolment, access to resources, and gender disaggregation—is scarce.
- Limited coordination between non-governmental organisations and government departments and services.
- Limited coordination between the school and family.

To address some of these gaps, the second phase of the study sought to explore stakeholders' perspectives and experiences of SEND in the country through:

- a. Semi-structured individual and group interviews with teachers from mainstream schools (n = 5) and special schools (n = 9), caregivers (n = 14), policymakers (n = 3), and a donor representative from UNICEF (n = 1).
- b. Focus group discussions conducted with learners with SEND (n = 28 learners).

Key findings indicate that teachers and caregivers predominantly hold deficit-based views of learners, often describing disability as an 'abnormality' and focusing on physical impairments. Positive intentions towards inclusion exist, but conceptual clarity is limited. Teacher preparedness is constrained by minimal pre-service exposure to SEND and limited continuous professional development opportunities, although informal peer-support networks demonstrate strong motivation. Students with SEND experience bullying, stigma, and barriers due to lack of learning materials, support tools, and accessible environments, yet they show strong resilience and a preference for inclusive mainstream schools. Policymakers and donors show strong support for inclusive education and knowledge of SEND categories, with multi-level governance structures and ongoing revisions to the 2015 Inclusive Education Policy reflecting the government's commitment. Donors emphasise sustainability and coordination, and positive attitudes towards EdTech integration are reported across stakeholders.

The key recommendations from this review are:

- 1.** Map special schools and inclusive education resource centres to identify resources, services, and gaps for better planning and coordination.
- 2.** Strengthen monitoring and evaluation of SEND initiatives to generate evidence on effectiveness and inform policy and programme decisions.
- 3.** Strengthen policy implementation and funding to ensure effective delivery of inclusive education.
- 4.** Build teacher capacity to implement inclusive and SEND-responsive teaching practices.

- 5.** Promote stakeholder engagement to amplify the voices of learners with SEND and their stakeholders, and to ensure that inclusion policies and practices reflect the lived experiences and needs of those with SEND.
- 6.** Strengthen monitoring, evaluation, and research to ensure data-driven decision-making.
- 7.** Enhance access to EdTech to promote inclusive and equitable quality education for all.

1. Introduction

This landscape analysis was developed in response to a request from the UK Foreign, Commonwealth & Development Office (FCDO) under a Ghana Accountable Grant, through the Partnership Beyond Aid (PBA) programme, to inform ongoing efforts to strengthen inclusive education systems in Ghana. The analysis sought to provide a systems-level understanding of the special educational needs and disabilities (SEND) ecosystem in Ghana, including policies, actors, delivery mechanisms, coordination gaps, and opportunities for reform.

The study followed a two-phase sequential research design: (1) a desk review of available literature and (2) empirical data collection. This section provides an overview of the purpose, methodology, and outline of this report.

1.1. Purpose and methodology of the landscape analysis

The landscape analysis seeks to provide a comprehensive overview of the policies, service delivery systems, infrastructure, capacity, socio-cultural dynamics, and stakeholder perspectives that collectively shape the SEND landscape in Ghana.

The study adopted a critical realist paradigm (see [Figure 1](#)), which acknowledges the different levels of reality and therefore allows researchers to integrate data from multiple sources to provide complementary insights into the social phenomenon under investigation ([Mukumbang, 2023](#); [Wiltshire, 2018](#)). Data was collected in two phases using both primary and secondary data collection methods to provide a comprehensive overview of the SEND landscape in Ghana.

Figure 1. Key steps to conduct the SEND landscape analysis

The initial phase consisted of a desk review of key literature on SEND in the country. Informed by the Cochrane rapid reviews interim guidance from the Cochrane rapid reviews methods group ([↑Garritty et al., 2021](#)), the desk review aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of what was known about policies, services, and resources on SEND at the time of the review. A deductive approach to data analysis, which entails the use of pre-ordinate categories or themes ([↑Proudfoot, 2023](#)), was followed. The analysis was guided by pre-existing themes that served as the analytical framework against which literature evidence was examined (see [↑Fife & Gossner, 2024](#)). These themes were developed and refined through consultative sessions with representatives from the Ministry of Education (MoE), the Special Education Division, and other partner organisations. The themes covered key areas, including policy and legislative environment; service provision and educational system overview; infrastructure and resource availability; socio-cultural and attitudinal context; stakeholder landscape; and technology access.

The second phase aimed to investigate the experiences and perspectives of key stakeholders on SEND in Ghana. This phase aimed to address an underexplored area in the literature on Ghana and in the broader international research context, which relates to the voices of learners with SEND as well as of stakeholders, perspectives, and local realities. Adopting a qualitative approach to research, data were collected through:

- a. Semi-structured interviews conducted with caregivers of learners with SEND (n = 14), teachers from mainstream schools (n = 5) and special schools (n = 9), policymakers (n = 3), and donors (n = 1).
- b. Focus group discussions conducted with learners with SEND (28 learners divided into three focus group discussion groups) aged between 15 and 20.

The study received ethical approval from the EdTech Hub's Ethics Committee and from the Ghana Education Service (GES). Prior to study commencement, participants were provided with study information and consent to participate was gained. For learners with SEND, verbal assent was obtained from the learners, while written informed consent was gained from their parents or legal guardians. The interviews and focus group discussions were recorded and transcribed. Where participants responded in their local language, the transcripts were translated into English.

Collected data was uploaded into NVivo 12 software and analysed using a reflexive Thematic Analysis approach ([↑Braun & Clarke, 2006](#)). Reflexive Thematic Analysis provided analytic and interpretative tools that allowed

the researchers to “produce analyses from relatively straightforward descriptive accounts to more complex, theoretically embedded ones” (↑[Braun & Clarke, 2022](#), p. 9). In presenting the findings, participants’ original words have been retained unless grammar or syntax errors affect comprehension.

2. Desk review findings

2.1 SEND definitions, categories, and provision

This section provides an overview of how the 2015 Inclusive Education Policy ([↑Ministry of Education, 2015a](#)) defines people with disabilities and learners with special educational needs, outlines the main types of disabilities recognised in policy, describes how SEND is identified in Ghana, and describes the schooling arrangements available to children with disabilities. It then covers key data related to access to education for children with SEND.

2.1.1 SEND definitions and types of disabilities

The 2015 Inclusive Education Policy defines people with disabilities as individuals “who have long-term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairments which, in interaction with various barriers, may hinder their full and effective participation in society on an equal basis with others” ([↑Ministry of Education, 2015a](#), p. 25). Under the Inclusive Education Policy, learners with special educational needs are defined broadly to include both learners with disabilities and learners without disabilities who are failing in school due to particular barriers that prevent them from achieving optimal progress in their learning ([↑Ministry of Education, 2015a](#)). The definition, therefore, places the focus on all learners who experience difficulties in their learning, including those whose challenges arise from barriers rather than disabilities. These barriers to learning may be socio-economic (e.g., children living on the streets), geographical (e.g., nomadic children), health-related (e.g., children living with chronic conditions such as sickle cell anaemia, epilepsy, and asthma), vulnerability-related (e.g., children exploited for financial purposes/in servitude), or related to giftedness (e.g., gifted and talented persons ([↑Ministry of Education, 2015a](#))). The policy adopts a broad definition of SEND, encompassing both disability-related needs and other forms of educational vulnerability. However, for the scope of this report, the analysis focuses on children with identified SEND categories (see [Box 1](#) below) to maintain analytical clarity and depth. [Box 1](#) outlines the types of disabilities recognised in the Inclusive Education Policy.

Box 1. *Types of disabilities recognised the Ministry of Education Inclusive Education Policy* ([↑Ministry of Education, 2015a](#))

- Intellectual/developmental disabilities
- Hearing impairment
- Visual impairment
- Physical impairment—motor and mobility impairment (including cerebral palsy)
- Autism spectrum disorder
- Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD)
- Specific learning difficulties (including dysgraphia, dyscalculia, dyspraxia, dyslexia)
- Social, emotional, and behavioural difficulties
- Epilepsy
- Multiple impairments
- Others (e.g., speech and language difficulties)

2.1.2 SEND identification

SEND identification and assessment remains a global challenge, particularly in low-and middle-income countries. While the purpose of identification is to determine the presence of an educational need, assessment aims to provide a detailed understanding of an individual's challenges and abilities across different domains (see [↑Antalek et al., 2025](#)). Worldwide, SEND identification involves a myriad of assessment tools and practices including formal diagnosis, screening tools, collaboration with SEND educators, parents, and external professionals, and classroom observations. At the national level, in the 2018/2019 academic year, the National Assessment Centre (NAC) in Ghana assessed 286 children, referring 79 for further evaluation and placing 115 in appropriate support arrangements ([↑Ministry of Education, 2019a](#)). [↑Good Governance Africa – West Africa \(2020\)](#) report that the Special Education Division, with support from UNICEF/USAID has restructured 10 regional assessment centres, which have been supplied with assorted assistive devices and basic screening materials. Also, the Ghana Education Service (GES) has procured 12 audiometers for hearing assessments and distributed them to all 10 regional assessment centres and the NAC. Further, the 2015 Inclusive Education Policy ([↑Ministry of Education, 2015a](#)) calls for the creation of assessment centres in all regions and districts of the country and mandates that teachers be trained in initial assessment to identify children's learning needs.

Nevertheless, evidence shows that there is no unified method for SEND identification in Ghana, especially at the school level ([↑Karr et al., 2022](#)). To

date, there is no published evidence documenting the screening and assessment tools used for SEND identification in the country. Most SEND assessments in Ghana take place at the country's assessment centres and a few specialised audiology and vision clinics. These centres, largely urban-based, include two focused on hearing and two multi-purpose facilities (↑[Karr et al., 2022](#)). Moreover, a study conducted by ↑[Ahiamenyo & NweahAckah Mochiah \(2022\)](#) indicates that teachers had limited knowledge of assessment practices and policies in Ghana. In examining early SEND identification in 25 public Kindergartens in the country, ↑[Soma et al. \(2023\)](#) identified several barriers to identification, including teachers' inadequate knowledge and lack of structured plans and strategies of identification. Furthermore, the accessibility of assessment centres is limited: a study involving 120 staff and clients across five centres in the country found that these centres were generally not accessible to children with SEND, creating another barrier to timely assessment and support (↑[Agbetorwoka, 2021](#)).

2.1.3 Schooling arrangements for children with SEND

The 2015 Inclusive Education Policy (↑[Ministry of Education, 2015a](#)) and the 2018–2030 Education Strategic Plan (↑[Ministry of Education, Ghana, 2019b](#)) promote inclusion for children with disabilities through both regular and special schools (see [Section 2.3.1](#)). The Inclusive Education Policy emphasises that learners with special educational needs should be included in regular (mainstream) schools wherever possible, while special schools are reserved for children with more complex needs (↑[Ministry of Education, 2015a](#)). The policy specifies that regular schools should be accessible to all children regardless of their physical, intellectual, social, emotional, linguistic or other conditions; however, if an assessment is conducted and it is found that a child will not benefit from attending regular classrooms, then that child should be placed in a special unit within a regular school or in a special school (↑[Ministry of Education, 2015a](#)). The *2018 Education Sector Performance Report* indicates that children with mild to moderate disabilities have been integrated into regular schools. As of the 2017/18 academic year, a total of 18,310 learners with special educational needs were enrolled in regular mainstream schools across 20 focus districts (↑[Ministry of Education, 2018a](#)). The 2018 education sector analysis shows that about 29,000 students with disabilities were registered in basic and secondary schools in 2016/2017, among which 21% were enrolled in special schools. The data indicate that children enrolled in special schools represent a very small proportion of total enrolment, ranging from 0.2% at the senior high school (SHS) level to 0.4% at the

primary, junior high school (JHS), and Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) levels. The report indicates that only 16% of schools report having at least one pupil with a disability, attributing this in part to delayed identification linked to limited teacher training in recognising disabilities ([↑Ministry of Education, 2018b](#)).

While regular schools are expected to collaboratively ensure that the schooling environment is child-friendly, accessible, and prepared to deliver inclusive education and strong referral services, the Inclusive Education Policy aims to transform special schools into resource centres that assist mainstream schools and special units in supporting children with severe disabilities ([↑Ministry of Education, 2015a](#)). Special schools are also tasked with working closely with assessment centres for periodic screening and ensuring that centre personnel are adequately trained ([↑Ministry of Education, 2015a](#)).

Inclusive education was introduced in Ghana in 2003 to promote access and participation of students with SEND in regular mainstream classrooms ([↑Opoku et al., 2017](#)). Since 2012, the GES, in partnership with UNICEF, has piloted inclusive education using the Inclusive Education Monitoring Tool (IEMT) to support policy adaptation. Initially implemented in 14 districts, the initiative has expanded to 24 districts and is currently in its third phase ([↑Opoku-Nkoom & Ackah-Jnr, 2023](#)). 2.2 School attendance for children with disabilities

The 2021 Ghana Population and Housing Census found that, of approximately 7.8 million children aged 5–15 years, 2.8% (219,022 children) experienced difficulties performing functions in the following domains: sight, hearing, physical, intellectual, self-care, and speech ([↑Ghana Statistical Service, 2023](#)). Additionally, 16.3% of these children with difficulties have never attended school, which is notably higher than the 8.6% national average for all children aged 5–15 who have never attended school ([↑Ghana Statistical Service, 2023](#)). While this figure is likely underestimated due to low detection and reporting rates, research shows that attendance rates for children with disabilities in Ghana is lower than that of children without disabilities at all levels of pre-tertiary education, with average rates for children with disabilities being 10 percentage points lower than for those without and the gap being most pronounced at the primary level ([↑Ministry of Education, 2018b](#)).

The [↑Ghana Statistical Service \(2023\)](#) reported notable geographical differences in attendance rates among children with SEND. For instance, fourteen districts in the Northern Region are home to over 25% of children with disabilities who have never attended school, and the Northern Region

also has the highest intra-regional disparities in attendance rates, with a range from 10.2% in the best-performing district to 72.5% in the worst-performing district (Gushegu Municipal). Meanwhile, regions such as Ahafo, Western, and Central Regions (in the south) have the lowest intra-regional disparities ([↑Ghana Statistical Service, 2023](#)).

Additionally, attendance rates varied by SEND type, with higher rates among learners with emotional disorders¹ and sight-only disabilities, and lower rates among learners with speech, physical, and intellectual disabilities ([↑Ministry of Education, 2018b](#)). For instance, the [↑Ghana Statistical Service \(2023\)](#) reports that in most districts in the country, 90% of children with severe sight difficulties have attended school. In 42 districts, among children aged 5 to 15 years with disabilities who have never attended school, more than half have severe speech disabilities ([↑Ghana Statistical Service, 2023](#)).

In addition to the attendance rates discussed above, the 2018 education sector analysis shows that progression rates for children with disabilities are relatively low, and that 31% of out-of-school children (OOSC) aged 17 are learners with disabilities, compared to 8% for OOSC aged 13 ([↑Ministry of Education, 2018b](#)). This reflects the persistent barriers learners with SEND face in accessing education. Later in this report, we discuss factors that affect both access to education and the quality of support provided to learners with SEND, including inadequate infrastructure and resources ([Section 2.5](#)), limited teacher training ([Section 2.6](#)), and stigma and discrimination ([Section 2.7](#)).

¹ 'Emotional disorders' is a term used to describe a range of disorders that affect emotional regulation and behaviour. Children with emotional disorders may display "irritability, frustration, impulsive actions, or difficulties focusing," which can affect their socioemotional development and educational experience ([↑Jacob, 2023](#)).

2.2 Policy and legislative environment

2.2.1 National legislation, policies, and plans

This section provides an overview of the legislation, policies, and plans that govern the SEND landscape in Ghana. [Table 1](#) below outlines the purpose and objectives of these national documents, key strategies established to improve inclusive education, and how the policies and plans are financed.

Table 1. *National SEND legislation, policies, and plans in Ghana*

National policy/strategy	Ministry/agency involved	Description
Persons with Disability Act (Act 715 of 2006)	National Council on Persons with Disability	<p>Purpose/objectives: The Persons with Disability Act was created to promote and protect the rights of persons with disabilities in Ghana. The act aims to ensure equal access to public services, employment, education, healthcare, and transportation for persons with disabilities (PWDs) (Parliament of Ghana, 2006).</p> <p>Sector: Education, Health, Social Welfare, Transportation</p> <p>Key SEND components: The Persons with Disability Act includes several provisions to improve education access and support for learners with disabilities, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) compulsory enrolment for children with disabilities; (2) designation of regional schools equipped with facilities to support learners with disabilities; (3) free education and establishment of special schools for PWDs excluded from formal schools; (4) appropriate training for those unable to continue formal education after pursuing basic education; (5) prohibition of discriminatory admission practices; (6) inclusion of special education into the curricula of technical, vocational, and teacher training institutions (Parliament of Ghana, 2006).

National policy/strategy	Ministry/agency involved	Description
Inclusive Education Policy (2015)	Ministry of Education Special Education Division of the Ghana Education Service (GES)	<p>Purpose/objectives: The 2015 Inclusive Education Policy outlines key policy objectives and strategies to improve the delivery and management of educational services to better respond to the diverse needs of learners with special educational needs (↑Ministry of Education, 2015a).</p> <p>Sector: Education</p> <p>SEND types: Intellectual/developmental disabilities; hearing impairment; visual impairment; physical impairment, e.g.,—motor and mobility impairment; autism spectrum disorder; attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD); specific learning difficulties; social, emotional, and behavioural difficulties; epilepsy, and multiple impairments (↑Ministry of Education, 2015a).</p> <p>In its definition of learners with special educational needs, the policy also includes learners without disabilities who are failing in school due to particular barriers.</p> <p>Key SEND components: The key strategies outlined in the policy document are structured around four main policy objectives:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Adapting education and related systems to ensure the inclusion of learners with special educational needs. (2) Promoting a learner-friendly environment to improve the quality of education for all. (3) Building capacity to support the effective implementation of inclusive education across Ghana. (4) Ensuring sustainability of inclusive education efforts (↑Ministry of Education, 2015a). <p>The Inclusive Education Policy was followed by an Implementation Plan that provided an overview of the expected deliverables for 2015–2019 (↑Ministry of Education, 2015b).</p>

National policy/strategy	Ministry/agency involved	Description
Education Strategic Plan (2018–030)	Ministry of Education	<p>Purpose/objectives: The Education Strategic Plan (ESP) provides an overall framework for improving the quality of education in Ghana. The ESP is structured around seven strategic goals, including but not limited to improving equitable access to and participation in quality basic and senior high school education; improving access to world-class tertiary education; and improving access to education for persons with disabilities, the vulnerable, and the talented (Ministry of Education, Ghana, 2019b).</p> <p>Sector: Education</p> <p>Key SEND components: Key SEND strategies outlined in the ESP include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Ensuring that existing educational institutions are designed or modified to improve opportunities for learners with SEND;■ Conducting sensitisation and advocacy efforts to promote understanding and acceptance of learners with SEND in schools and communities;■ Building the capacity of schools and communities to support early identification and provide appropriate infrastructure;■ Implementing social intervention programmes to support children with disabilities;■ Training teachers to effectively teach learners with disabilities;■ Establishing strong administrative and financing structures to support the rollout of inclusive education policies.

National policy/strategy	Ministry/agency involved	Description
Early Childhood Education (ECE) Policy	Ministry of Education	<p>Purpose/objectives: The development of the ECE policy is in line with the policy objectives outlined in the 2018–2030 ESP. The policy goals and objectives are organised around six action areas, including: planning and management, curriculum development and implementation, teacher pre-service education and training, in-service education and training, family and community engagement, child-friendly safe spaces, and monitoring, regulation and quality assurance (↑Ministry of Education, 2020a).</p> <p>Sector: Education</p> <p>Key SEND components: Key SEND strategies outlined in the ECE policy include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Promoting equitable access to KG services, with emphasis on enrolment at the right age and enrolment of children with SEND.■ Ensuring kindergarten (KG) facilities are accessible and inclusive for all children.■ Strengthening the use of inclusive play-based pedagogy modules for state and non-state KGs

National policy/strategy	Ministry/agency involved	Description
Early Childhood Care and Development (ECCD) Policy 2025	Ministry of Gender, Children and Social Protection	<p>Purpose/objectives: The policy aims to promote the survival, growth, development and protection of all young children (0–8 years old) so that they can thrive and achieve their full potential. It focuses on six domains: health, nutrition, early learning, responsive caregiving, safety and security, and inclusion (↑Ministry of Gender, Children and Social Protection, 2025).</p> <p>Sector: Child development</p> <p>Key SEND components: Key SEND strategies outlined in the ECCD policy include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Facilitating and ensuring the inclusion of all young children (0–8 years old) with disabilities and other vulnerable children in all aspects of life.■ Identifying and providing for the critical needs of young children (0-8 years old) with disabilities and other vulnerable children and their primary caregivers.■ Ensuring early childhood programmes and services are accessible and friendly to all children with disabilities and other vulnerable children and are implemented equitably. (↑Ministry of Gender, Children and Social Protection, 2025)

National policy/strategy	Ministry/agency involved	Description
Education Sector Medium-Term Development Plan (ESMTDP) 2018–2021	Ministry of Education	<p>Purpose/objectives: The 2018–2021 Education Sector Medium-Term Development Plan was informed by both the 2018–2030 ESP and the National Medium-Term Development Policy Framework. The ESMTDP includes an action plan outlining activities to be conducted during the 2018–2021 period to achieve the policy objectives and strategies outlined in the ESP (↑Ministry of Education, 2019c).</p> <p>Sector: Education</p> <p>Key SEND components: Key SEND activities outlined in the 2018–2021 Education Sector Medium-Term Development Plan include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Developing and disseminating disability-friendly minimum standards for school infrastructural provision. ■ Establishing/converting part of existing structures into resource centres ■ Providing learning equipment, materials, and tools for assessment in needy areas. ■ Sensitising parents and communities to help them understand and accept learners with disabilities, and with special and additional needs. ■ Training district teacher support teams to conduct cascade training at the school level on ensuring a safe learning environment for learners with disabilities. ■ Developing training manuals and guidelines for early detection, continuous review, and referral processes. ■ Strengthening inter-ministerial collaboration to identify marginalised communities. ■ Reviewing the national curriculum to ensure it appropriately accommodates special educational needs and talented students. ■ Establishing a steering committee to mobilise resources at all levels to support inclusive education.

2.2.2 Financing for the Inclusive Education Policy, the Education Strategic Plan, and their SEND objectives

The Inclusive Education Policy explicitly states that financial resources for the implementation and operationalisation of the policy will come from the following sources: the Government of Ghana, development partners, local non-governmental organisations, civil society organisations, faith-based organisations, philanthropists, and the private sector, with the principal funder being the Government of Ghana ([↑Ministry of Education, 2015a](#)). The policy also explains that, to fund implementation, a proportion of the national revenue should be set aside, and stipulates cost-sharing among the various government stakeholders responsible for implementation ([↑Ministry of Education, 2015a](#)).

However, despite these stipulations, financing for the Inclusive Education Policy is insufficient, thereby hindering effective implementation ([↑Asamoah et al., 2021](#)). For example, the five-year cost implementation plan (2015–2019) estimated a total requirement of GHS 378 million to deliver the planned inclusive education interventions ([↑Ministry of Education, 2015a](#)). Nevertheless, the actual government allocation was GHS 59.84 million (see [Table 2](#) below). Analysis of the available evidence reveals that expenditure on inclusive and special education fluctuated considerably between 2016 and 2025 ([↑Ministry of Education, 2016](#); [↑Ministry of Education, 2017](#); [Ministry of Education, 2018b](#); [Ministry of Education, 2019d](#); [Ministry of Education, 2020b](#); [Ministry of Education, 2021](#); [Ministry of Education, 2022](#); [Ministry of Education, 2023](#); [↑Ministry of Education, 2024a](#); [Ministry of Education, 2025](#)). Notably, 2018 and 2024 stand out as years of extremely low funding, with only GHS 17 thousand (0.00019% of the total education expenditure) in 2018 ([↑Ministry of Education, 2018c](#)) and GHS 673 thousand (0.0023% of the total education expenditure) in 2024 ([↑Ministry of Education, 2024a](#)).

Table 2. *Inclusive education funding (GHS) and % of total education, 2016–2025*

Year	Inclusive and special education expenditure (GHS)	Total education expenditure (GHS)	% of total
2016	26,998,739	6,532,352,027	0.41%
2017	23,510,778	8,330,099,829	0.28%
2018	17,111	9,258,839,827	0.00019%
2019	9,325,975	11,205,401,222	0.083%
2020	16,880,722	13,301,182,692	0.13%
2021	5,348,933	15,631,637,855	0.034%
2022	487,156	17,786,818,000	0.0027%
2023	210,263,094	22,902,600,753	0.92%
2024	673,429	29,514,197,713	0.0023%
2025	44,362,228	31,772,464,382	0.14%
Total	337,868,165	337,868,165	0.20%

Thus, over the period 2016–2025, inclusive education expenditure accounted for approximately 0.20% of the total education budget. Specifically, the funding was allocated to the following activities: social intervention programmes; learning and teaching materials; publications, campaigns and programmes; internal management of the organisation; and supervision and inspection of education delivery (see [Ministry of Education, 2025](#)). Although the overall pool of funds allocated to education expenditure is limited, other factors, such as competing demands and government priorities, also influence the allocation of financial resources for implementation of the SEND strategies outlined above ([Asamoah et al., 2021](#)).

The 2018–2030 Education Strategic Plan outlines potential sources of funding for financing its policy strategies, including its SEND components. The potential sources include a mix of government budget allocations, internally generated funds (such as fees and levies from tertiary education students), and external sources, including donor contributions and loans ([Ministry of Education, Ghana, 2019b](#)). The ESP outlined specific costs for inclusive and special education activities from 2018 to 2021. However,

despite these planned allocations, the ESP acknowledges that domestic financing has been inadequate to support the effective implementation of SEND activities ([↑Ministry of Education, Ghana, 2019b](#)). The plan further anticipates a growing funding gap across the education system between 2018 and 2030 and presents two financing scenarios to assess the resources needed for implementation. Scenario 1 assumes modest growth in available resources. Under this scenario, the budget gap rises from 2.5% in 2018 to over 11% in 2020–2021, narrows to 7.9% in 2025, but increases again to 13.7% in 2030. Scenario 2 assumes slightly higher initial resources and faster medium-term growth, which reduces the shortfall, peaking at 10.1% in 2019 and declining to 0.8% in 2025, though a 3% gap remains in 2030. These scenarios highlight the need for timely and sufficient funding, including potential external support, to fully realise ESP priorities.

One example of an external financing mechanism that supports the implementation of the ESP is the Ghana Accountability for Learning Outcomes Project (GALOP), which is funded by the World Bank, the Global Partnership for Education, and other development partners ([↑World Bank, 2019](#)). Given that inclusive education for learners with SEND is a recognised component of the ESP, GALOP actively funds this through multiple targeted mechanisms. Project documentation shows that GALOP has allocated resources to provide teaching and learning materials specifically designed for learners with SEND and for teachers trained to support greater disability inclusion in schools ([↑World Bank, 2019](#)). The project has also directed funding towards in-service teacher training on disability inclusiveness and kindergarten teacher training that incorporates disability screening and inclusive pedagogy ([↑World Bank, 2019](#)). Furthermore, through the Education Outcomes Fund mechanism, GALOP's Additional Financing phase incentivises inclusive practices by giving preferential weighting in the procurement process to service providers who demonstrate strong capacity to provide interventions for learners with disabilities ([↑World Bank, 2019](#)).

2.3 Service delivery and system architecture

2.3.1 Governance structures supporting special education in Ghana

This section provides an overview of the governance structures responsible for special education in Ghana. While the Ministry of Education (MoE) and its agencies are the primary bodies responsible for implementing inclusive education, the MoE also collaborates with several other relevant ministries, agencies, departments, non-governmental organisations (NGO), private

sector organisations, associations, and umbrella coalitions of Persons with Disabilities (PWDs) involved in education, human rights, and child protection programmes. [Table 3](#) below outlines the roles and responsibilities of the governmental bodies delivering special education in Ghana.

Table 3. Governance structures supporting special education in Ghana

Governance structures	Roles and responsibilities
Ministry of Education (MoE)	The Ministry of Education (MoE) provides overall leadership for inclusive and special education in Ghana. It is responsible for policy development, implementation, review, coordination, and the monitoring and evaluation of special education interventions. The MoE coordinates closely with the Ministry of Finance to allocate resources to SEND programmes, and it also oversees curriculum review and training and professional development to ensure national curricula and pedagogical approaches are inclusive, relevant and responsive to the needs of learners with SEND (↑Ministry of Education, 2015a ; ↑Ministry of Education, Ghana, 2019b).
Special Education Division of Ghana Education Service	The Special Education Division of the Ghana Education Service (GES) is the primary agency responsible for inclusive and special education. The division oversees the implementation of the Inclusive Education Policy through national, regional, and decentralised district structures (↑Ministry of Education, 2015b). Among other responsibilities, the division ensures that schools are equipped with appropriate teaching and learning materials (including assistive technologies), that schools use relevant pedagogical models, and that it collaborates with the Ghana Health Services to conduct training for health staff (↑Ministry of Education, 2015b).
Ministry of Health/Ghana Health Service	The Ministry of Health and Ghana Health Service collaborate closely with the Ministry of Education to support the early identification and assessment of disabilities among pupils and provide appropriate health care services for all children. This includes screening, treatment, and referral mechanisms to ensure timely intervention for children with disabilities. Government-funded schools, (known as public schools) in Ghana require an assessment from the national assessment centre in order to admit learners(↑Ministry of Education, 2015b).

Governance structures	Roles and responsibilities
Ministry of Gender, Children and Social Protection (MoGCSP)	The Ministry of Gender, Children and Social Protection (MoGCSP) works closely with the Ministry of Education to ensure a coordinated, effective approach to early identification and support for children with disabilities. The MoGCSP ensures that social protection programmes are delivered effectively, with specific attention to vulnerable groups of children, including children with SEND (↑Ministry of Education, 2015a ; ↑Ministry of Education, 2019b)
National Council on Persons with Disability (NCPD)	The National Council on Persons with Disability plays an advocacy role to ensure the implementation of the Inclusive Education policy. The council advocates for resources to support programmes addressing SEND (↑Ministry of Education, 2015a).
Metropolitan, Municipal and District Assemblies (MMDA)	The Metropolitan, Municipal, and District Assemblies (MMDA) collaborate with the Ministry of Education to support the implementation of the Inclusive Education policy, particularly at the local and school level. The MMDA are responsible for mainstreaming inclusive and special education issues highlighted in the Inclusive Education policy in their medium-term development plans and for allocating resources to the District Assembly Common Fund and the disability fund to support the education of children and adults with disabilities (↑Ministry of Education, 2015a).
Ministry of Finance	The Ministry of Finance works closely with the Ministry of Education to ensure that adequate resources are allocated to support the implementation of inclusive and special education programmes (↑Ministry of Education, 2015a).
Ministry of Transport	The Ministry of Transport collaborates with the Ministry of Education to provide resources to support the implementation of inclusive education, particularly with children with disabilities. In collaboration with the Ghana Education Service, the Ministry of Transport is tasked with providing basic schools with buses or bussing services; providing designated disability-friendly buses for

Governance structures	Roles and responsibilities
	children with physical disabilities; and providing infrastructure such as sound-ambers to guide those with visual impairments (↑Ministry of Education, 2015a).
Ministry of Local Government & Rural Development	The Ministry of Local Government & Rural Development liaises with the Ministry of Education to set aside funds to support various inclusive education strategies, including ensuring the provision of necessary school infrastructure to meet the needs of Persons with Disability (↑Ministry of Education, 2015a).
National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NaCCA)	The National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NaCCA) is an independent statutory body that is responsible for curriculum design, development, and revision. The Standards-Based Curriculum developed by the NaCCA explicitly references inclusion and non-discrimination, and the NaCCA and Ghana Education Service have validated Ghana's Harmonised Sign Language Curriculum (↑Amnesty International, 2026).

The Inclusive Education Policy also outlines the roles of non-governmental organisations, development partners, and the private sector in the delivery of SEND programmes in Ghana. These partners are tasked with providing both technical and financial support in key areas such as the development of adapted teaching and learning materials; the provision of basic screening materials and assistive devices; support for teacher capacity-building initiatives; the construction of physically and environmentally accessible schools, and the implementation of research, monitoring, and evaluation activities ([↑Ministry of Education, 2015a](#)).

With the development of policies and strategic plans that clearly define the roles and responsibilities of various governmental and non-governmental stakeholders, the government of Ghana has taken significant steps towards the effective implementation of inclusive and special education. Since SEND interventions are often delivered across multiple sectors and levels of government, having clear policies and plans improves coordination among stakeholders, ultimately leading to more effective implementation.

However, although this is an important start, factors such as political commitment, adequate and sustainable financing, technical capabilities, and continued collaboration are essential to ensure that these policy objectives and strategies translate to meaningful improvements in the service delivery of SEND interventions ([Abane et al, 2025](#); [Hayford & Asare, 2025](#)).

2.4 Infrastructure and resources

Ghana's education system is structured around two main pathways: special schools and mainstream schools. Learners with severe disabilities are primarily educated in special schools, where they receive support from specialised teachers and paraprofessionals ([↑Amponteng et al., 2025](#)).

While the 2015 Inclusive Education policy aims to ensure that school infrastructure and teaching and learning materials are accessible for all learners with SEND, both regular and special education schools in Ghana still face significant challenges in providing adequate infrastructure and resources to effectively support learners with SEND. Research shows that the lack of adequate infrastructure and resources to meet the diverse needs of learners with SEND significantly affects the quality of education that can be provided and highlights the urgent need for targeted interventions to make inclusive education a reality (see [↑Adjanku, 2020](#)).

For instance, a significant proportion of schools lack basic accessibility features, such as handrails, ramps, and accessible classrooms and WASH facilities. According to the 2018 Education Sector analysis, the vast majority of regular schools did not have handrails, and only **8% were equipped with ramps** ([↑Ministry of Education, 2018b](#)). Similarly, most regular Senior High Schools (SHS) were not equipped with either ramps or handrails. While special schools tend to perform relatively better in terms of accessible infrastructure, only **32% were equipped with ramps and 23% equipped with handrails**, showing that gaps still remain even within institutions designed for learners with disabilities ([↑Ministry of Education, 2018b](#)). Furthermore, only 44% of regular basic schools have functional water facilities, while 46% of SHS have no hand-washing facilities. These limitations frequently result in injuries among learners with SEND ([↑Gyimah, 2021](#)).

In a study examining the educational challenges faced by children with visual impairments, researchers found that 39.1% of participants were dissatisfied with their school facilities ([↑Kyei-Gyamfi et al., 2025](#)). Factors that contributed to dissatisfaction with school facilities included poor school infrastructure (including broken classroom furniture and classrooms arranged poorly or inconsistently, which pose safety hazards), overcrowding in classrooms, and unsafe school compounds. Teachers and children with visual impairments detailed several specific concerns regarding unsafe school conditions, including how difficult it is for these learners to navigate school grounds during rainy seasons and the risks this poses to them.

Furthermore, with many schools being severely under-resourced, access to assistive technologies is very limited. In [↑Kyei-Gyamfi et al. \(2025\)](#), teachers and children with visual impairments discussed the lack of availability, costliness, inadequacy, and outdatedness of teaching and learning materials to support the children, including resources like Braille materials, Braille sheets, voice recorders, and magnifiers for learners with low vision. Teachers also discussed how the lack of access to these resources affects the ability of children with visual impairments to keep up with their peers with no disabilities, and how many children become demotivated as a result of these conditions.

2.4.1 Special schools and facilities

Provision of formal education for learners with SEND is delivered through a network of government-managed special schools, a small number of private and NGO-run institutions, and a limited system of assessment and resource centres, all coordinated by the Special Education Division of the

Ghana Education Service. The Special Education Division operates through seven functional units covering inclusive education, visual impairment, hearing impairment, learning disability, intellectual and developmental disability, a Braille press unit, and the National Assessment and Resource Centre, which carries the mandate for routine disability screening and placement recommendations at the national level ([↑Ministry of Education, 2015a](#)).

Government-managed special schools serve three primary disability categories: hearing impairment, visual impairment, and intellectual and developmental disability (IDD), spanning basic, secondary, and vocational levels. A small but distinct private and NGO sector supplements public provisions, particularly for learners with autism and IDD in urban areas. [Table 4](#) below presents the known institutions across both sectors by region and disability focus.

Table 4. *Special schools in Ghana by sector, disability focus, and region.* Sources: ↑Ametepee & Anastasiou, 2015; ↑Ghana Education Service, 2021; ↑Ghana Schools, 2019; ↑Pats Tune, 2024; ↑The Epicentre, n. d; ↑UNESCO, 2021; ↑Woodfield Manor, n. d.

School	Sector	Location	Region	Disability Focus	Level
Akropong School for the Blind (est. 1945)	Public/GES	Akropong-Akwapi m	Eastern	Visual impairment	KG–JHS, Vocational, Adult Rehabilitation
Demonstration School for the Deaf—Demodeaf (est. 1959)	Public/GES	Mampong-Akuape m	Eastern	Hearing impairment; Deafblind unit (est. 1978)	KG–JHS
Mampong School for the Deaf—SHTS (est. 1975)	Public/GES	Mampong, Akuapem North	Eastern	Hearing impairment	Senior High Technical
Akwapim School for the Deaf	Public/GES	Akwapim	Eastern	Hearing impairment	Basic
Mampong/Akwapim Sec Tech for the Deaf	Public/GES	Akwapim Mampong, Akwapim South	Eastern	Hearing impairment	Secondary/Technical
Unit School for the Deaf	Public/GES	New Juaben	Eastern	Hearing impairment	Basic
Cape Coast School for the Deaf (incl. Blind Unit, est. 2001/02)	Public/GES	Cape Coast	Central	Hearing impairment; Visual impairment (unit)	Basic
Dzorwulu Special School (incl. Autism Resource Centre)	Public/GES	Accra Metro	Greater Accra	Intellectual & developmental disability; Autism	Basic, Vocational

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School	Sector	Location	Region	Disability Focus	Level
Volta School for the Deaf	Public/GES	Hohoe	Volta	Hearing impairment	Basic
Ashanti School for the Deaf	Public/GES	Jamasi, Adansi East	Ashanti	Hearing impairment	Basic
Garden City Special School (est. 1977)	Public/GES	Asokore-Mampong, Kumasi	Ashanti	Intellectual & developmental disability	Basic, Vocational
Bechem School for the Deaf (incl. Technical Institute)	Public/GES	Tano South	Ahafo	Hearing impairment	KG–JHS, Vocational
Wenchi School for the Blind	Public/GES	Wenchi	Bono	Visual impairment	Basic
Tamale School for the Deaf	Public/GES	Tamale	Northern	Hearing impairment	Basic
Gbeogo School for the Deaf	Public/GES	Tongo, Bolgatanga	Upper East	Hearing impairment	Basic
Wa School for the Blind	Public/GES	Wa	Upper West	Visual impairment	Basic
Wa School for the Deaf	Public/GES	Wa	Upper West	Hearing impairment	Basic
Takoradi School for the Deaf	Public/GES	Sekondi-Takoradi	Western	Hearing impairment	Basic
New Horizon Special School (est. 1972)	Private/NGO	Cantonments, Accra	Greater Accra	Intellectual disability, Autism	KG–JHS, Vocational (adults 18+)

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School	Sector	Location	Region	Disability Focus	Level
Woodfield Manor Autism & Special Needs School	Private	Frafraha, Adenta, Accra	Greater Accra	Autism, special needs	Basic
Multikids Inclusive Academy (est. 2010)	Private	Accra	Greater Accra	Autism, ADHD, dyslexia, IDD	Basic
The Epicentre Special School (est. 2013)	NGO	New Gbawe, Accra	Greater Accra	Autism, IDD, cerebral palsy, Down syndrome	Basic, rehabilitation
Autism Training Centre	Private	Accra	Greater Accra	Autism	Basic

It should be noted that the total number of special schools recorded in official documents varies across reporting periods, partly reflecting differences in definitional scope. The [Ministry of Education \(2024a\)](#) reports that there are 31 public special schools in the country, of which four are second-cycle schools². However, the Education Sector Performance report ([Ministry of Education, 2019a](#)) identifies 41 special schools (13 schools for learners with hearing impairments, 7 schools for learners with vision impairments, 12 schools for learners with intellectual disabilities, 1 senior high school for learners with hearing impairments, and 8 integrated senior high schools) with a total enrolment of 7620 learners.

Research conducted by the [Ministry of Education \(2019a\)](#) revealed a modest but consistent increase in total enrolment across all school types between 2016/17 and 2018/19, rising from 6,899 to 7,620. However, enrolment in schools for learners with visual impairments declined marginally over this same period, from 759 to 737, potentially indicating pressures on capacity or access for this population. More recent enrolment data disaggregated by school type and disability category is not publicly available, which limits assessment of trends beyond 2018/19.

Furthermore, geographic access to these institutions is profoundly uneven. In a study on access to special education facilities for children aged 5–15 with learning difficulties, the [Ghana Statistical Service \(2023\)](#) found that the availability of such facilities varied significantly by location. For example, in 5 out of 16 regions in Ghana—North East, Savannah, Bono, Oti, and Western North Regions—there are no special education facilities ([Ghana Statistical Service, 2023](#)). Special education schools are heavily concentrated in the southern part and the eastern corridor of the country with clear clusters in the Ashanti, Eastern, and Greater Accra Regions. While the study sheds light on significant geographical disparities in the availability of special education facilities, it does not provide insights into the underlying reasons for these differences.

Assessment centre provision similarly falls far short of national need. The National Assessment and Resource Centre within the Special Education Division is the only nationally designated government assessment facility, while a network of Regional Assessment Centres is intended to carry out annual health screening and referrals. UNICEF has supported the equipping of these regional centres with assistive devices, including hearing aids, glasses, wheelchairs, and basic screening materials

² In Ghana, “pupils must take the Basic Education Certification Examination (BECE) at the end of Junior High School to get placed into a second cycle school. The second cycle consists of three years of Senior High School (SHS) or Technical and Vocational Education (TVET)” ([Stenzel et al., 2024](#), p. 2).

(↑UNESCO, n. d.). However, in 2010, only four special education assessment centres existed nationally, with no documented evidence that district-level coverage had been achieved, as envisaged by the Education Strategic Plan 2003–2015 (↑Ametepee & Anastasiou, 2015). The absence of publicly accessible, comprehensive and updated data on assessment centre coverage is itself a significant gap in the evidence base. In 2023, the founder of the Africa Dyslexia Organisation publicly called on the government to establish assessment centres across all 16 regions, noting that private disability assessments cost a minimum of GHS 600—an amount far beyond the reach of most families (↑Bonney & Konadu-Boakye, 2022).

The education sector performance report outlines that the Special Education Division unit is working to convert part of existing special schools and regional assessment centres into inclusive education resource centres, supported by a Disability Trust Fund grant and in collaboration with partners such as the World Bank and UNICEF (↑Ministry of Education, 2019a).

2.5 Teacher and capacity training

Teacher training and professional development in inclusive education remains a key priority in policy, research, and practice, as teacher preparation influences their knowledge, skills, beliefs, attitudes, and motivation to promote students' learning (↑Ackah-Jnr et al., 2025).

This section examines teacher preparation, available support mechanisms, and teacher readiness for inclusive education as evidenced by recent studies, especially in the context of Ghana's ongoing efforts to integrate inclusive practices into its education system.

2.5.1 Pre-service teacher preparation for inclusive classrooms

Teacher preparation for basic and secondary education in Ghana is delivered through initial teacher education institutions. While the Colleges of Education award Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.) degrees following the transition from the three-year Diploma in Basic Education (DBE) to a four-year B.Ed degree. From 2018 to 2019, universities offered B.Ed degrees and postgraduate degrees, including Postgraduate Diplomas in Education and other education certificates (↑Naami & Mort, 2023). Comprehensive teacher training is a key factor that enables the effective promotion of inclusive education in Ghana (↑Nketsia & Saloviita, 2013). The 2015 Inclusive Education Policy requires all pre-service teacher training courses to include

inclusive education training to equip teachers with the requisite knowledge and pedagogical skills to meet the needs of learners with SEND. Under the former three-year DBE curriculum, all initial teacher training colleges integrated a 'two-credit compulsory course' on special needs and inclusive education ([Ametepee & Anastasiou, 2015](#)). However, this curriculum has since been replaced. Under reforms initiated by the MoE and Transforming Teacher Education and Learning (T-TEL) programme, from 2018 to 2019, colleges of education transitioned to a four-year B.Ed. degree. Drawing on teacher educator and teacher trainee perspectives on this course, [Nketsia et al. \(2020\)](#) found that most teacher educators (85%) and pre-service teachers (66%) considered it inadequate for developing inclusive knowledge and practices. Many educators noted complaints about the course's theoretical focus, which was also found to emphasise a medical model of SEND.

Furthermore, although the inclusive education components have been incorporated into the T-TEL initiative—a pre-service teacher training programme—research suggests that the curriculum and teaching materials in colleges of education do not adequately address the needs of learners with SEND. More precisely, [Naami & Mort \(2023\)](#) found that disability is not explicitly mentioned in any of the four learning outcomes of the equity and inclusivity cross-cutting pillar of the B.Ed curriculum, and that the observation checklist and reflective journals do not create adequate space for student teachers to reflect on disability. The curriculum's instruction for student teachers to identify "school and student characteristics that act as barriers to learning" was further critiqued for reproducing an individual rather than a social model of disability. Further, the school environment, classroom, lessons, class management, and assessment were all found to lack inclusivity ([Naami & Mort, 2023, p.5](#)). A recent study conducted by [Opoku and Nketsia \(2025\)](#) found that while most pre-service teachers reported exposure to inclusive education during their training, only a few felt adequately prepared to implement inclusive teaching strategies in the classroom. [Opoku-Nkoom & Dogbe \(2020\)](#) also showed that pre-service teachers hold strong appreciation for the core principles of inclusion. Nevertheless, many of those pre-service teachers continued to frame inclusion narrowly through an impairment-based lens. Such a limited focus raises important concerns, as "focusing only on some students, rather than on all, is contrary to the principles of inclusive education" ([Messiou, 2017, p. 146](#)). This suggests a limited emphasis on other students with special educational needs such as neurodivergent students, students with intellectual and developmental disorders as defined by the 2015 Inclusive Education Policy ([Ministry of Education, 2015a](#)).

2.5.2 Training, support mechanisms, and professional development opportunities for teachers in inclusive settings

Professional training opportunities for teachers in inclusive education have increased in recent years, largely due to national policy efforts and international development partner support. Nevertheless, the 2018 Education Sector Performance Report ([↑Ministry of Education, 2018a](#)) identifies the need for greater investment in special and inclusive education and outlines a multipronged approach to capacity-building for educators.

Despite these efforts, many schools still lack the physical infrastructure, adapted materials, and trained personnel needed for effective inclusive teaching. The Education Sector Performance Report acknowledges that inclusive education is under-resourced and unevenly implemented across regions ([↑Ministry of Education, 2018a](#)).

A report produced for [↑Good Governance Africa – West Africa \(2020\)](#) outlines that the Special Education Division unit in collaboration with UNICEF has developed an inclusive education In-Service Education and Training module. The module covers topics such as awareness of inclusive education and Ghana's inclusive education policy, strategies for supporting learners in schools, and the identification and referral of children with SEND ([↑UNESCO, 2021](#)). Nevertheless, there is currently no evidence on the module's implementation, impact, or effectiveness.

2.5.3 Teacher self-efficacy beliefs and attitudes

Teachers' attitudes and self-efficacy, namely their "beliefs in their ability to effectively handle the tasks, obligations, and challenges related to their professional activity", are central to shaping teaching practices and academic outcomes ([↑Barni et al., 2019](#), p. 1). [↑Amponteng et al. \(2026\)](#) suggest that teacher self-efficacy significantly predicts behaviour towards inclusive education. Studies on teacher attitudes and self-efficacy in Ghana have yielded mixed findings.

Research conducted by [↑Kuyini et al. \(2020\)](#) suggests that teachers often hold relatively negative attitudes towards inclusion and report moderate self-efficacy in implementing inclusive practices. [↑Opoku et al. \(2022\)](#) found that some private school teachers in Ghana teach learners with SEND despite having no confidence in their own capabilities. Consistent with these findings, [↑Dabone et al. \(2023\)](#) reported low levels of teachers' self-efficacy, which were significantly correlated with the challenges that teachers face in inclusive settings. With regard to teachers' attitudes, research indicates that teachers in Ghana hold negative attitudes towards

the inclusion of learners with SEND ([↑Kotor et al., 2022](#)). This is particularly true of older and male teachers ([↑Butakor et al., 2020](#)) and therefore potentially indicative of teachers' preference for placing those learners in special schools.

Conversely, a cross-cultural study investigating teachers' attitudes towards inclusion in Ghana, Germany, and Spain, [↑Mónico et al. \(2020\)](#) demonstrated that teachers from the three countries exhibited positive attitudes towards inclusion. Nevertheless, teachers from Spain and Germany were reported to have slightly more positive attitudes than those from Ghana in most cases.

2.6 Socio-cultural context

The socio-cultural context in a given country profoundly shapes learners' experiences, particularly their access to education, retention in schools, and learning outcomes. This section examines how these socio-cultural dynamics, along with gender, geography, socio-economic status, and the type of SEND, affect learners' education in Ghana.

2.6.1 Influence of cultural norms and traditional beliefs on perceptions of children with disabilities and their right to education

Traditional and religious beliefs in Ghana greatly impact societal attitudes towards children with disabilities and provide an environment in which stigma and discrimination prevent the full social participation of these individuals ([↑Ocran, 2022](#)). Research demonstrates that in Ghana, SEND is often equated with disability or learners with SEND are seen as belonging to a faulty group ([↑Odame et al., 2025](#)), rather than as students with special needs, and individuals are labelled using humiliating or discriminatory terms ([↑Achuroa, 2019](#)). This is mainly because these individuals are often viewed through a superstitious lens that attributes SEND to spiritual causes such as curses, ancestral anger, or divine wrath ([↑Mills, 2020](#); [↑Mantey, 2017](#)). In some families, young people with visible and pronounced disabilities (physical and intellectual) are often kept out of the public domain because of shame and fear of stigma, which limits their access to education and, in extreme cases, can even lead to them being harmed or killed ([↑Grischow et al., 2019](#)).

In an analysis of the education sector, the [↑Ministry of Education \(2018b\)](#) reported that stigma and discrimination are significant obstacles to access and quality of education for children with disabilities. Concerted and ongoing efforts are needed to modify entrenched cultural attitudes

towards children with SEND and ensure that they are acknowledged as having an entitlement to education on an equal basis with all children ([↑Gomda et al., 2022](#)). Programmes such as the community sensitisation and awareness-raising programmes facilitated by the Education Strategic Plan (2018–2030) work towards the acceptance and understanding of learners with SEND, but they are not widely available, especially in remote areas ([↑Ministry of Education, 2019a](#)).

2.6.2 Impact of gender, geography, socio-economic status, and type of SEND on access, retention, and learning experiences

This section provides an overview of how factors such as gender, geographic location, socio-economic status, and type of disability intersect to shape access to education and the educational experiences of children with SEND.

Gender and educational access

Gender disparities greatly affect the access to education for learners with SEND in Ghana ([↑Global Call to Action Against Poverty & Ghana Federation of Organisations of Persons with Disabilities \(GFD\), 2020](#)). Evidence indicates that, across different age groups, the proportion of females with SEND is generally higher than that of males ([↑Ghana Statistical Service, 2024](#)). However, no data is currently available to disaggregate the enrolment of children with SEND by gender, limiting our understanding of gender differences in school participation. Nevertheless, the available research shows that cultural norms promote boys' education. Gender norms in Ghana are deeply rooted in sociocultural and economic systems and strongly influence parental attitudes towards their children's education ([↑Nartey et al., 2025](#)). This is particularly evident in low-income families where male children are expected to reap more economic benefits from education than their female counterparts ([↑Boadu, 2000](#); [↑Donkor et al., 2019](#); [↑Handicap International, 2021](#); [↑UNGEI, 2017](#); [↑Yotebieng, 2021](#)); [↑Nartey et al. \(2025\)](#) show that parents often prioritise sons' education while withdrawing their daughters from education for caregiving duties, early marriages, or income-generating labour. In addition, in some regions, factors such as sexual harassment and abuse, seasonal migration, and teenage pregnancy were found to contribute to low retention rates of girls in education ([↑Nartey et al., 2022](#); [↑van de Waal et al., 2024](#)).

Geographical location and access to education

Worldwide, geographical location, particularly the urban–rural divide, is a major determinant of access to education for children with SEND

(↑[Cumming et al., 2022](#)). While inclusive education policies are formulated at the national level, their implementation and effectiveness may vary substantially across different locations. In Ghana, research shows that local environments in rural northern communities constrain children's access to schooling and learning (↑[Nkrumah et al., 2026](#)). Furthermore, special schools that meet accessibility standards are largely concentrated in major urban areas. Consequently, many children with SEND living in rural areas face significant barriers to school attendance, particularly due to transportation constraints (↑[Gomda et al., 2022](#)).

Rural schools, which are less difficult to reach of learners with physical disabilities, generally lack the most basic amenities, such as ramps, accessible toilet facilities, and assistive technologies (↑[Danson et al., 2012](#)). A study by ↑[Adjanku \(2020\)](#) found that children with SEND in rural Ghana encounter barriers, such as long distances to school and a shortage of qualified teachers, which discourage attendance. While travelling challenges affect all learners in rural areas, they pose an even greater barrier for learners with SEND. For instance, the lack of transport in remote areas creates more isolation for learners with mobility disabilities (↑[Alimo et al., 2024](#)). There are also urban–rural differences in the availability of special education services. Several urban areas have specialised schools or resource centres, while rural areas depend on mainstream schools, which usually do not cater to learners with SEND (↑[Ghana Statistical Service, 2023](#)). This geographic disparity plays out in other rural areas, where families may be less knowledgeable about their children's rights to education or have less access to advocacy resources (↑[Akyeampong et al., 2007](#)). In addition, rural communities invariably have to grapple with cultural barriers that hinder families from seeking education for their children due to stigma associated with SEND (↑[Reynolds, 2010](#)).

Socio-economic status and educational outcomes

Socio-economic status is a strong factor influencing enrolment and retention in school for learners with SEND in Ghana. Families of low socio-economic status face economic barriers, including costs of school attendance, transportation, and specialised medical equipment, such as wheelchairs or hearing aids (↑[Liu, 2020](#)). Poverty exacerbates the stigma attached to SEND, where some families even see it as a curse, preventing investment in the education of children with SEND (↑[Bernardes et al., 2016](#)). This prejudice is exacerbated among poor families, where resources are focused on the non-disabled siblings. Parents' inability to interact with schools and lack of agency to challenge schools to meet the needs of their children due to poverty also perpetuates exclusion (↑[Oranga et al., 2022](#)).

Type of SEND and learning experiences

The type and severity of SEND affects learners' educational experiences in Ghana. Research shows that children with intellectual and/or severe physical difficulties face exclusion because of lack of facilities and teacher preparedness ([↑Karr et al., 2020](#)). For instance, children with vision or hearing impairments would need Braille materials and/or sign language interpretation, which are not readily available, especially in rural schools ([↑Opoku et al., 2015](#)). In addition, many educators lack the knowledge necessary to instruct learners with intellectual difficulties in a curriculum that meets their needs, such as how to differentiate and incorporate universal design for learning principles ([↑Amoah & Yeboah, 2023](#)), which support learners with SEND by creating learning environments that accommodate their diverse needs, and offer teachers multiple ways to present course content and knowledge ([↑Han & Lei, 2024](#)).

Intersections of factors

[↑Bronfenbrenner's \(1979\)](#) conceptualisation of the "ecology of human development" provides a useful theoretical framework for understanding how the development of children with SEND, as well as their education, are influenced by environmental factors. Bronfenbrenner referred to the environment as a nested ecosystem, which was "affected by relations between these settings, and by the larger contexts in which the settings are embedded" (as quoted in [↑Fanshawe, 2025](#), p. 76). Research findings at the microsystem level reveal that barriers such as early identification constraints, teachers' attitudes towards students with SEND, accessibility to the physical environment, and the accessibility of learning materials have a detrimental effect on their education ([↑Kotor et al., 2022](#); [↑Soma et al., 2023](#); [↑Masuku et al., 2024](#)). At the mesosystem level, collaboration among teachers and between teachers and parents may have a significant impact on students with SEND (see [↑Amoako et al., 2021](#)). At the exosystem, education policies and structures may have different impacts on learners, despite the paucity of empirical evidence on the direct influence of different policies on SEND education. Further, parents' education level was reported to impact the education of their children ([↑Ghanney, 2018](#)). At the macrosystem level, prejudice, societal misconception, and stigma are reported to impact the education of children with SEND as well as the care they receive ([↑Hervie, 2023](#); [↑Seidu et al., 2025](#)). [↑Amponteng et al. \(2025\)](#) suggest that from the perspective of [↑Bronfenbrenner's \(1979\)](#) theory, several barriers negatively influence inclusive education in Ghana.

Thus, findings from different research studies suggest that the interplay of gender, geography, socio-economic status, and SEND creates

compounded barriers for learners and often results in their marginalisation and increased school dropout rates (†Zickafoose et al., 2025). A research study conducted by †Senoo et al. (2024) exploring barriers to inclusive education of children with autism in Ghana confirms that, despite policies and strategies, there are practical challenges in coordination, collaboration, and policy execution, including lack of collaboration among professionals and systems that hinder inclusive education in the country. The authors acknowledge that there is very little evidence on inclusion implementation. Studies have recognised that intersectionality complicates educational inequalities, especially for rural girls with severe disabilities, who are the most vulnerable to exclusion (†Wolbring & Nasir, 2024). This ecological system theory shows that the intersection between different barriers in a child's environment, such as home, school, and society, adds an extra layer of complexity for children with SEND, as navigating multiple systems with different challenges can increase the barriers and impact their education.

2.7. SEND actors and interventions

This section provides an overview of selected non-governmental actors delivering SEND interventions in Ghana and highlights key areas of the interventions, with a particular focus on initiatives implemented in collaboration with the Ministry of Education and its agencies.

Table 5. *Non-governmental stakeholders supporting SEND in Ghana*

Non-governmental stakeholder	Roles and responsibilities
ANOPA/RYTHM Foundation	<p>Overview: The ANOPA/RYTHM Foundation supports children with visual and hearing impairments in developing a love for learning through sports-based teaching methods, aiming to reduce truancy and delinquency and improve school retention. (↑ANOPA Ghana, 2021).</p> <p>Key activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Community sensitisation ■ Inclusive sports ■ Vocational training for children and youth with disabilities <p>Domains: Physical and intellectual disabilities</p> <p>Geography: Central Region</p>
Autism Compassion Africa	<p>Overview: Autism Compassion Africa provides evidence-based Applied Behaviour Analysis (ABA) therapy, caregiver training, and community outreach to support children with autism and address the critical service gap in the region (↑Autism Compassion Africa, no date).</p> <p>Key activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ ABA therapy sessions ■ Training for teachers/parents ■ Awareness campaigns on autism ■ Referrals for multisectoral support <p>Domains: Autism</p> <p>Geography: Regional (West Africa)</p>

Non-governmental stakeholder	Roles and responsibilities
<p>Center for Learning and Childhood Development (CLCD)—Ghana</p>	<p>Overview: A research-driven NGO focused on improving early childhood development and education for urban poor and rural communities through programmes in health, developmental delays, and basic education (↑CLCD, no date).</p> <p>Key activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ School bridging/inclusion support ■ Public education campaigns ■ Physiotherapy collaboration ■ Volunteer school assistance <p>Domains: Developmental disabilities</p> <p>Geography: Nationwide</p>
<p>Ghana National Association of the Deaf (GNAD) and Inclusion Ghana</p>	<p>Overview: Disabled Persons’ Organisations and civil society networks advocating for inclusive schooling and rights-based programmes.</p> <p>Key activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Advocacy for inclusive education and rights-based programmes <p>Target group: Various learners including those with hearing, intellectual, or physical disabilities.</p> <p>Implementing ministries/organisations: GNAD and Inclusion Ghana</p>
<p>Inclusion Ghana</p>	<p>Overview: A network advocating for the rights and inclusion of persons with intellectual and developmental disabilities and their families, with strong representation and partnerships at both national and international levels (↑Inclusion Ghana, 2024).</p> <p>Key activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Coordinated advocacy campaigns ■ Capacity building for member NGOs ■ Community outreach ■ Inclusive education monitoring <p>Domains: Individuals and families affected by intellectual and developmental disabilities</p> <p>Geography: Nationwide</p>

Non-governmental stakeholder	Roles and responsibilities
<p>Sparklers Foundation (Association of SEN Centres)</p>	<p>Overview: An organisation providing inclusive education, training, and support for individuals and families managing autism and other learning difficulties (↑Sparklers Foundation, 2026).</p> <p>Key activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Network support ■ Resource sharing ■ Teacher mentorship ■ Advocacy for standardised service delivery <p>Domains: Autism</p> <p>Geography: Nationwide</p>
<p>Special Attention Project (SAP Ghana)</p>	<p>Overview: An NGO championing the inclusion of children with specific learning difficulties in mainstream education through research, awareness, training, and reintegration support (↑SAP Ghana, 2020).</p> <p>Key activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Inclusive education ■ Early detection of learning difficulties ■ Teacher training ■ Advocacy <p>Domains: Cognitive disabilities</p> <p>Geography: Greater Accra</p>

Non-governmental stakeholder	Roles and responsibilities
Voice Ghana	<p>Overview: An advocacy organisation that campaigns for the rights of people with disabilities in Ghana. Voice Ghana promotes access to quality education for learners with SEND and also provides capacity building training for self-help groups in Ghana (↑Devex, no date).</p> <p>Key activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Capacity building ■ Education and outreach on issues of inclusion and gender justice <p>Domains: Diverse disabilities</p> <p>Geography: Volta Region</p>
DeafCanTalk	<p>Overview: DeafCanTalk offers a mobile app that leverages cutting-edge technology for real-time sign language translation, educational resources, and a supportive community platform.</p> <p>Key activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Capacity building ■ Education and outreach on issues of inclusion and gender justice <p>Domains: Hearing impairment</p> <p>Geography: Ghana</p>
Special Olympics Ghana	<p>Overview: An NGO focused on supporting learners with intellectual disabilities across Ghana</p> <p>Key activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ General Health screening in public schools ■ Parental engagement and counselling ■ Training in sports for the summer and winter Olympics <p>Domains: Intellectual disabilities</p> <p>Geography: Ghana</p>

2.7.1. Initiatives supporting SEND in Ghana

Table 6. Key initiatives supporting SEND

SEND initiative	Description
Ghanaian Sign Language Curriculum	<p>Overview: Aims to standardise sign language instruction across pre-tertiary schools and ensure inclusive education for all learners (↑Ghana Education Service, 2025).</p> <p>Implementation year and status: 2025—Ongoing</p> <p>Target group: Children with mild-to-moderate disabilities, special learning needs.</p> <p>Implementing ministries/organisations: Ghana Education Service Special Education Division, National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NaCCA), and Ghana National Association of the Deaf (GNAD)</p>
UNICEF Championing Inclusive Practices (Early Grade Focus)	<p>Overview: Aims to improve teachers' knowledge of inclusive practices and increase support for all early grade learners, particularly those with disabilities (↑UNICEF Ghana, 2022).</p> <p>Implementation year and status: 2019–2021</p> <p>Target group: First-grade teachers, headteachers, and district-level staff in Ada West and West Gonja Districts (↑UNICEF Ghana, 2022).</p> <p>Implementing ministries/organisations: UNICEF Ghana, Ghana Education Service, and Inclusive Development Partners.</p>
Mastercard Foundation & International Centre for Evidence in Disability (ICED) Inclusion Research	<p>Overview: Focuses on policy mapping and providing key insights into the inclusion of people with disabilities in education and employment (↑University of Ghana et al., 2023).</p> <p>Implementation year and status: 2023 (completed)</p> <p>Target group: Youth with disabilities transitioning to employment and tertiary education.</p> <p>Implementing ministries/organisations: University of Ghana, International Centre for Evidence in Disability (ICED), and Mastercard Foundation.</p>
Transforming, Teaching, Education & Learning	<p>Overview: A pre-service teacher training programme within the colleges of education in Ghana that includes elements of inclusive education (↑T-TEL, 2021).</p>

SEND initiative	Description
<p>(T-TEL) Pre-Service Reform & Inclusion Emphasis³</p>	<p>Implementation year and status: 2014–2020</p> <p>Target group: All 46 public colleges of education in Ghana</p> <p>Implementing ministries/organisations: UK’s Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Office, Ministry of Education (Ghana Tertiary Education Commission), and Cambridge Education.</p>
<p>Mathematics Curriculum for Visually Impaired (VI) in Secondary High Schools (SHS)</p>	<p>Overview: The National Council for Curriculum and Assessment NaCCA has developed a Mathematics Senior High School (SHS) curriculum for blind learners, which is currently being trialled in Okuapemman SHS, where T-TEL has helped to supply tactile materials and other learning aids (↑T-TEL, 2025).</p> <p>Implementation year and status: 2024-ongoing</p> <p>Target group: SHS students with visual impairments</p> <p>Implementing ministries/organisations: NaCCA, T-TEL</p>

³ See <https://t-tel.org/>. Retrieved 17 February 2026.

2.7.2. Evidence on what works

Table 6 above presents a range of SEND initiatives to support SEND undertaken in Ghana. While these interventions provide critical support for the education of children with SEND, there is limited formal evidence on their effectiveness. Most initiatives have been documented descriptively, focusing on activities and implementation processes rather than measured outcomes.

One intervention that has been formally evaluated is the T-TEL programme. While [Nketsia et al. \(2020\)](#) found that most teacher educators and pre-service teachers considered it inadequate for developing inclusive knowledge and practices, [Dorgbetor and Nordzi \(2025\)](#) found that student teachers trained under T-TEL significantly outperformed their counterparts from the previous system in professional competence ($p < .001$). Further, [Ananga et al. \(2021\)](#) conducted an impact assessment of T-TEL's virtual learning task force for teacher education adopted during the closure of colleges of education in Ghana due to Covid-19. The study found that eLearning has improved participation among student teachers with SEND, promoted more inclusive lessons, and increased their autonomy.

While evidence on effectiveness in Ghana is limited, globally, models such as resource centres are statistically associated with higher academic attainment and stronger school belonging ([Cook & Boddy, 2026](#)). Interventions such as Jot-A-Dot technology for students with visual impairments in Lesotho in ([School-to-School International \(STS\), no date](#)), Mental health promotion programmes (Zippy's Friends in SEND schools) in England ([Unwin et al., 2018](#)), individualised programmes ([Van Herwegen et al., 2025](#)), and EdTech interventions to support foundational learning in Sierra Leone ([Lurvink & Pitchford, 2023](#)) were found to raise the educational outcomes of children with SEND.

2.8 Access to EdTech

The integration of EdTech in education has gained significant momentum in Ghana, driven by concerted efforts from the government and NGOs to improve access, quality, and equity in learning. Nevertheless, there remains very limited evidence on how EdTech is being used specifically to support the inclusion of children with SEND ([Layachi & Plaut, 2025](#)). However, the Special Education Division is developing a SEND dashboard in collaboration with Craft Education,⁴ which is anticipated to improve data

⁴ Craft Education is a social enterprise located in Accra, Ghana that is developing Africa's first teletherapy (SaaS) platform called Hunu ([Craft Education, n. d.](#)).

availability and support future evidence generation. This section provides an overview of the status of EdTech access for teachers and caregivers of learners with SEND, and learners themselves, drawing on existing research and national policy frameworks.

2.8.1 Teachers

The Special Education Division, in collaboration with UNICEF, has developed the Inclusive Education Monitoring Tool (IEMT), which collects both qualitative and quantitative information on schools. Data is primarily gathered by head teachers, with input from teachers during school meetings, and is subsequently verified by circuit supervisors during routine school visits. Supervisors observe classrooms, inspect facilities, and informally interview teachers and children with and without disabilities, providing feedback to school staff. A comments section within the checklist allows head teachers and supervisors to note school-specific issues. It intends to help schools self-assess and reflect on their inclusiveness ([↑Otaah et al., 2013](#)). The IEMT can identify barriers to inclusion in schools and has a 4-point Likert scale ([↑Opoku-Nkoom & Ackah-Jnr, 2023](#)).

Nevertheless, access to assistive technology and EdTech tools among teachers in Ghana remain limited and unevenly distributed ([↑Nyavor & Amaniampong, 2024](#)). While some inclusive and special schools possess basic ICT infrastructure, access to devices such as screen readers, Braille displays, and augmentative and alternative communication (AAC) tools is not widespread ([↑Nyavor & Amaniampong, 2024](#)). Evidence also suggests that many teachers have limited exposure to assistive technologies during both pre-service and in-service training, leading to low confidence and skill levels in using such tools effectively ([↑Nyavor & Amaniampong, 2024](#); [Vanderpuye, 2023](#)).

The 2015 Inclusive Education Policy advocates for the integration of assistive technologies in classrooms; however, this aspiration is not reflected in widespread implementation ([↑National Centre for Research Into Basic Education, 2025](#)). The 2018–2030 Education Strategic Plan (ESP) has inclusive education as a goal, but makes limited reference to inclusive EdTech or digital accessibility standards. Funding constraints, coupled with low prioritisation of assistive technology in resource allocation, have left schools dependent on donor support for the acquisition of devices ([↑Fordjour, 2022](#)). These project-based interventions are often unsustainable and geographically skewed towards urban centres ([↑Hayford & Asare, 2025](#)).

Infrastructure challenges also hamper EdTech use in classrooms. Many schools, especially in rural areas, face unreliable electricity, poor internet connectivity, and limited technical support, all of which affect the functionality and maintenance of EdTech tools ([↑Soma et al., 2021](#)). Teachers in such contexts are unable to consistently or meaningfully integrate technology into their teaching practices ([↑Soma et al., 2021](#)).

2.8.2 Learners

For learners with SEND, access to EdTech is constrained by the availability, affordability, and relevance of content. Most public schools lack dedicated assistive devices, and when tools are available, they are often outdated or incompatible with current learning platforms ([↑Nantwi & Asamoah, 2025](#)). Research by [↑Lanbon et al. \(2022\)](#) highlights the unequal distribution of EdTech resources, with children in the northern and upper regions of Ghana having significantly less access than those in Greater Accra or Ashanti.

The content on national digital platforms such as iCampusGH or iBox (see [↑Center for National Distance Learning & Open Schooling, no date](#); [↑Mallet et al., 2022](#)) is rarely adapted for learners with specific disabilities. These platforms lack accessibility features such as narration, simplified text, or Ghanaian Sign Language, limiting their relevance and usability for learners with SEND.

Parents are typically required to purchase assistive devices privately, which creates a significant affordability barrier ([↑Joshua Annor et al., 2019](#)). Households in low-income communities are particularly disadvantaged, leading to a reliance on low-tech or non-digital alternatives that are less effective in supporting learning.

2.8.3 Parents and caregivers

Caregivers play a critical role in the learning journeys of children with SEND, especially in home-based learning. However, their ability to support digital learning is constrained by low digital literacy and minimal access to inclusive EdTech ([↑Joshua Annor et al., 2019](#)). There is a paucity of research evidence regarding caregivers of learners with SEND and their access to, or experiences with, EdTech in the country. For instance, no previous study has investigated the use of WhatsApp communities among caregivers of children with SEND.

Table 7. Key EdTech for SEND/inclusive education initiatives in Ghana

EdTech Initiative	Description
DeafCan Talk	<p>Overview: An AI application that uses algorithms to convert spoken language into text and vice versa. Launched in Ghana in June 2023 during the UNICEF StartupLab demonstration day, it is the first application of its kind in the country. The software currently has 87 active users, with numbers steadily growing (UNICEF, 2023).</p> <p>Implementation year and status: 2023—ongoing</p> <p>Target group: Individuals with hearing impairments</p> <p>Implementing ministries/organisations: N/A</p>
Introduction to Computer Basics for Visually Impaired (ICBVI)	<p>Overview: A course that delivers training in basic and intermediate digital skills for people with vision impairment (Kaiyettar, 2024)</p> <p>Implementation year and status: 2023—ongoing</p> <p>Target group: Implementing ministries/organisations: the ITU Telecommunication Development Bureau and the STMicroelectronics Foundation (ST Foundation)</p>

3. Empirical research findings

This section presents findings from the semi-structured individual and group interviews with teachers from **mainstream** (n = 5) and **special** (n = 9) schools, caregivers (n = 14), policymakers (n = 3), a donor representative from UNICEF (n = 1), and focus group discussions with learners with SEND (n = 3) conducted by the team in Ghana. Data from each stakeholder group was analysed separately, and themes are reported by group.

3.1 Teachers of learners with SEND: Perspectives and experiences

How disability is conceptualised is critical, as the language individuals use to describe those with SEND influences their expectations and interactions with them (↑[Haegele & Hodge, 2016](#)). Participant teachers reflected on their own understanding of SEND, and attitudes towards learners with SEND. The participants' accounts revealed a deficit-based understanding of SEND, in which learners were defined by what they were perceived as 'unable' to do. As one teacher from a special school put it, "it means that there is something lacking somewhere. Limitation, such as communication, social integration, physical ability, hearing ability."

Disability was framed by teachers as an individual abnormality, with several teachers from both special and mainstream schools using language that positioned learners with SEND as differing from the assumed 'norm'. For instance, teachers argued that learners with SEND "are different from their normal or regular peers" and "not able to do something that a [typically developing] person has to do". These definitions emphasise incompetence and deficit-based perceptions provided by the medical model of disability. Based on a medical model, disability is understood as "an individual and/or a medical phenomenon that results in limited functioning that is seen as deficient" (↑[Haegele & Hodge, 2016](#), p. 195). With regard to terminology, teachers reported that, alongside stigmatised labels, the terms vision impairment (VI) or visually impaired were frequently used to refer to learners with a wide range of SEND. When explaining this practice, one teacher noted that the teaching staff at their school were trained as specialists in VI, which contributed to the categorisation of all learners as '*VI learners*', regardless of their specific needs.

Conceptualisations of SEND were strongly influenced by biomedical explanations. Participants commonly ascribed disability to illness, injury, or congenital conditions. One teacher attributed SEND generally to "*certain actions taken by the parent during pregnancy, maybe during birth or*

immediately after birth, that results in certain conditions.” In contrast, there was minimal recognition of environmental, social, or structural factors that might contribute to learners’ difficulties. Further, when asked to name examples of SEND, teachers showed strong emphasis on physical impairments (e.g., vision impairment, cerebral palsy) over other forms of SEND. Awareness of specific SEND categories, particularly neurodivergent difficulties such as autism, ADHD, or dyslexia, was limited, which may explain the biomedical understanding of causes of SEND. Many teachers from both special and mainstream schools appeared to interpret a wide range of learning difficulties as a singular form of ‘disability’, indicating a lack of awareness of neurodivergence.

Alongside participants’ language, which suggested a deficit-based understanding of SEND, and stigma towards learners with SEND, the teachers expressed strong values of care, unity, and moral responsibility towards learners with SEND, often emphasising notions such as “*we are all one*”. When asked about their perspectives on inclusion, many teachers expressed broadly positive attitudes towards inclusive education. However, these positive intentions were accompanied by limited conceptual clarity, with responses often referring to the physical placement of learners with SEND and a very limited reference to inclusion principles, approaches, or practices. This aligns with the distinction between affective and cognitive dimensions of teacher readiness, as teachers may value inclusion yet lack the knowledge and practical skills to implement it effectively. In contrast, some teachers expressed a preference for segregated special education settings, expressing concerns about resource availability and the risk of reduced engagement among learners identified as typically developing. For instance, according to one teacher at a special school:

“In our communities, we don't mix the normal kids with the special kids, [...] it's going to cause distraction in the class.”

This accords with previous research findings, which show mixed views and attitudes regarding inclusive education in the country (see [Section 2.6.3](#)).

3.1.1. Teacher preparedness for SEND and inclusive education

Teachers’ interviews focused on the teachers’ pre-service education and professional development opportunities. Teachers from both mainstream and special schools reported that their pre-service education provided limited preparation for working with learners with SEND. As one teacher put it: “*The training from the college of education is not enough.*” Participants from mainstream schools outlined that issues related to SEND

and inclusion were minimally addressed during their initial teacher education. Most teachers referred to having completed only a single course, commonly described as an ‘introduction to special needs’, which they perceived as insufficient for developing practical competencies in inclusive teaching. Teachers from special schools similarly expressed concerns regarding the adequacy of their pre-service training. Although they had specialised in special education, participants reported that their preparation was largely theoretical, with limited opportunities to engage in practical or applied learning related to inclusive classroom practices. Across both groups, there was consensus that pre-service education did not adequately prepare education professionals to meet the demands of increasingly inclusive educational settings. Teachers highlighted a gap between theoretical knowledge acquired during training and the practical skills required to support learners with diverse needs in real classroom contexts.

Teachers reported taking independent initiatives to develop their knowledge and understanding of SEND and inclusive practices. In the absence of adequate formal training, participants described adopting a range of informal strategies to support their professional learning. These included consulting Special Education Resource Teachers⁵ and seeking guidance from more knowledgeable colleagues. Teachers also noted that informal peer-support networks often emerged organically within schools, facilitating the sharing of practical advice and classroom strategies. Teachers reported the following.

“We meet and discuss strategies that we can use to teach the children.”

“Most of the time, we meet with the resource teachers, [...] they have been enlightening us about development that comes in the course of education.”

The interviews indicated that such collaboration was largely driven by practical necessity, particularly in contexts where teachers felt insufficiently prepared by formal SEND training. In addition to collaborating with colleagues, teachers often pursue their own development through the internet, YouTube, and online courses. For instance, as one teacher noted, *“Most of the time, for me personally, I go online to learn.”*

Further, some teachers reported attending in-service training opportunities (e.g., workshops) provided by the Special Education Division

⁵ Special Education Resource Teachers in Ghana are assigned to specific schools and circuits to support learners with special needs and disabilities (see [Nyavor, 2024](#)).

or by NGOs. However, interview data indicated that awareness of these opportunities was uneven, as several participants noted that they were only informed of training sessions when these were organised directly at their school. This suggests a limited dissemination of information about available professional learning opportunities beyond individual school settings. Alongside limited training opportunities and resources, teachers described the role of resource room teachers in mainstream schools as largely confined to content transcription. This may suggest that the pedagogical expertise of those teachers is underutilised.

When asked about the use of EdTech tools to support learners with SEND, teachers reported very limited access to EdTech resources within their schools. Despite this limitation, teachers expressed openness and a positive attitude towards integrating EdTech in their schools to promote inclusive education. As teachers put it: “This school doesn't have computers to do such tasks for these learners”; and “Technology will be the solution.”

3.1.2 Inclusion barriers and challenges

Participants consistently reported several challenges that hinder inclusive education in their schools. These barriers included policy-practice gaps, resources and infrastructure challenges, training and capacity limitations, knowledge gaps, and societal attitudes.

While many participants acknowledged the existence of inclusive education policies, they consistently noted a lack of practical guidance to support implementation at the school and classroom levels. Classroom realities were described as misaligned with policy expectations. As one teacher put it: “The policies are there—we cannot say that the policies do not exist. We do not need additional policies; we need to strengthen implementation.” Further, the interview data indicates severe limitations in the availability of teaching resources, the support services, the accessibility of school environments, and overcrowded classrooms, which, as one teacher claimed, “don't meet the expectation of SEND.” Challenges related to limited training opportunities, low levels of awareness, and a shortage of qualified personnel in schools were reported to affect not only learners but also teachers’ motivation. As a result, a few teachers reported considering leaving their teaching positions and “moving out of the country”. In addition, strong societal stigma towards learners with SEND was frequently reported, alongside negative perceptions of teachers who work closely with these learners. In demonstrating this stigma, some teachers outlined:

“In the community, they see them as snake children [...] they call them snake children.”⁶

“When you [referring to parents] have a child [with SEND] in your house, you hide the child.”

“They [parents] locked them [children with SEND] in the house.”

3.2 Caregivers of children with SEND: Perspectives and experiences

In line with teachers’ conceptualisations of SEND, caregivers showed a deficit-based understanding by focusing on what the learners ‘cannot do’. Learners with SEND were frequently described as ‘abnormal’ and according to some parents, they “can’t meet a normal [...] a normal way of living for a person”. SEND was commonly attributed to physical or medical conditions, with particular emphasis on pregnancy-related issues. Some caregivers referred to spiritual causes. As one caregiver explained, “Some parents have been committing sin [...] maybe a parent has sinned against someone.” The caregivers reported some stigmatised labels that are used in their societies to refer to learners with SEND, such as the label “water children”, which is used to refer to children who were perceived as “sick from God”. The label may suggest that those children are thought to be marked by spiritual forces linked to water. In a similar vein, the caregivers demonstrated a limited understanding of neurodivergence and a focus on visible, physical difficulties. While participants expressed mixed views about inclusive versus special schools for their children, most preferred special schools. In explaining their preference, a caregiver noted, “The special education is the best for special needs children because [...] their learning capabilities will be different.”

3.2.1 Caregivers’ experiences

Caregiver participants reported receiving limited assistance, with most support services focusing on medical interventions rather than psychosocial support. Few educational support opportunities were reported, and those that existed were provided either by the school or by NGOs. While some teachers reported facing educational challenges in the school, as the school “did not understand their conditions” and they were

⁶ “Snake children” is a spiritual term used in some West African communities to describe children with special educational needs and disabilities (SEND). Within certain indigenous religious belief systems, SEND may be interpreted as resulting from ancestral or spiritual forces. Further, the term is linked to observed early motor difficulties—such as poor neck control, low muscle tone, or slithering movements—are culturally interpreted through a spiritual lens rather than a biomedical framework (see [Bayat, 2015](#)).

unable to take the school's "assessment", others were satisfied with the school's support.

The participants reported several challenges that they faced as caregivers of children with SEND. These challenges included diagnosis challenges, emotional challenges, financial challenges, and societal stigma.

3.3 Learners with SEND: Perspectives and experiences

Learners' accounts suggest that their educational experiences are shaped by the interplay between social and infrastructural challenges, economic barriers, and personal resilience within special and mainstream school settings. Several learners reported experiencing bullying and social rejection within the school settings as well as in the broader society. These experiences are captured in the following quotations:

"When I go to church, they don't want me to sit in front and nobody wants to sit beside me."

"They laugh at the fact that I don't have one leg. They dance in a way to make fun of how I move".

"They bully me for the fact that I am bigger than usual".

The reported negative social interactions contributed to the learners' marginalisation and affected their participation.

In addition, many learners reported facing significant learning challenges arising from economic hardship and structural challenges. As one student put it, "I don't come to school when my dad doesn't have money because I have to walk to the school." Notably, learners' accounts placed limited emphasis on educational, social, and psychological support and challenges, focusing instead on economic hardship. Further, some learners described how certain teacher practices limited their opportunities to engage and participate in classroom activities. For instance, these learners reported the following.

"Sometimes I want to learn in class, but my madam tells me to go and help other people."

“Sometimes Sir A gives us work to do [unrelated to our learning], and he also gives us marks after the work.”

Despite the reported challenges, the learners’ accounts showed strong resilience and motivation. Many learners reported that the bullying and the barriers they faced strengthened their determination. As one student put it:

“When I was left out, I cried. But when I finished crying, I sat down and thought about it, and I studied hard because I wanted to become a great person in the future.”

3.4 Policymakers’ perspectives

Group as well as individual interviews (n = 3) were conducted with members from the Ministry of Education’s Pre-tertiary Directorate, the Special Education Division of the Ghana Education Service, and the Ministry of Education’s unit in charge of Infrastructure.

3.4.1 Supporting inclusive education: Perspectives, practices, and challenges

The participants indicated a strong support for inclusive education and demonstrated a good knowledge of SEND categories. Their responses also reflected a medical-based understanding, emphasising biological factors in explaining SEND behaviours. Further, some participants argued that some behaviours exhibited by children with SEND may not align with typical expectations. They noted that inclusive environments can help children acquire positive behaviours, because, as one participant put it:

“They are thinking differently, and they have different mindsets [...] If they are with their regular counterparts, they learn from one another, and peers have influence on one another [...] they will begin to learn or learn some of their behaviour patterns and then pick the correct ones.”

Some participants reported partial compliance of schools in the country with accessibility standards, as one participant said: “Some schools do, but not all the schools. Some schools meet halfway.” Another participant claimed that “most of the schools are still not accessible”. Nevertheless, all participants emphasised that several initiatives are underway to enhance accessibility in schools. On the other hand, a participant from the infrastructure unit noted that, following the implementation of the Persons with Disability Act, 2006, Act 715 ([↑Parliament of Ghana, 2006](#)), all school designs from 2016 onward are fully accessible and equipped with the

required accessibility features. This suggests that several initiatives are underway to ensure that new schools meet accessibility standards.

As for the learning resources, some participants reported that some assistive technology tools are available to support learners with visual impairments. However, as noted by another participant: “Learners who are neurodivergent are the ones that have been neglected when it comes to procurement of assistive technology and other things,” which may suggest that less attention is given to learners with less apparent difficulties, as the teaching and learning resources available “do not capture the needs of learners who are neurodivergent”. Regarding capacity building, one participant acknowledged the limitations posed by funding, stating: “We have not done much in that direction in the sense that we do not have enough funds to cover the whole country.” Despite these constraints, they noted that the Special Education Division organises “refresher courses, in-service training [...] on how to manage inclusive classrooms”. The participants noted that pre-service training may sometimes fall behind emerging SEND issues, acknowledging that: “Because the emerging issues are moving very fast. Maybe we've not caught up with these emerging issues.” They emphasised the importance of building professional learning communities to support ongoing learning and help educators stay current with new developments.

The participants outlined several challenges that hinder the education of children with SEND in the country, including funding and resource constraints, religious and cultural beliefs which may lead to stigma and rejection, awareness barriers, inadequate teacher knowledge, shortage of human resources and trained special education teachers, large class sizes, high student-to-teacher ratios, and parental denial of children’s needs.

The participants identified EdTech as a key opportunity for enhancing teaching and learning in inclusive schools, as one participant put it: “technology will be a game changer”.

3.4.2 Institutional and government structures supporting inclusive education

Participants described a multi-level governance structure through which responsibilities for inclusive education are organised and implemented across national, regional, district, and school levels. At the national level, the ministry plays a central role in developing inclusive education policies and programmes. These policies are implemented through the Special Education Division of the Ghana Education Service, which translates national policy directions into programmes, training initiatives, and

activities to support learners with SEND in both special and mainstream schools. Next, national-level trainers provide training to regional core trainers, who then transfer the knowledge and skills to district special education coordinators and district support teams. These teams subsequently work with schools to implement inclusive education practices at the school level. Circuit supervisors monitor the activities of special education coordinators within their circuits, while school headteachers are responsible for ensuring that all learners benefit from teaching and learning activities in their schools.

Participants further emphasised the existence of monitoring and accountability mechanisms across different levels of governance. National authorities, the Ghana Education Service, and national school inspectors conduct monitoring activities to assess the implementation of inclusive education policies in schools. The participants provided practical examples of the cross-sector collaboration in implementing inclusive education, such as the 'My first Day at School' programme, which involved multiple actors. While the Ministry of Education (MoE) provided teaching and learning materials to kindergartens, the Ghana Health Service conducted early screening for disabilities.

3.4.3 Policy reforms, initiatives, and alignment with the UN Sustainable Development Goal 4

The ongoing revision of the 2015 Inclusive Education Policy was highlighted as evidence of the government's commitment to improving the education of children with SEND. Participants reported that the new draft is aligned with the UN Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), which aims at ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education and promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all, and is expected to introduce stronger implementation measures ([↑United Nations, no date](#)). A Technical Working Group was convened to guide the revision process, including representatives from the Ghana Federation of Disability Organisations, the National Council on Persons with Disability, the Ministry of Education, the Ghana Education Service, the National Schools Inspectorate Authority, and the National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NaCCA). According to the participants, the new draft, currently under review, places greater emphasis on addressing infrastructure gaps, resource constraints, and service delivery challenges, while shifting focus from special schools towards inclusive mainstream education. As one participant put it:

"The policy direction on the revised policy [...] moved from having special schools to having inclusive schools. Move all children from

the special schools into the mainstream schools. Then, probably turn the special schools into resource centres.”

3.4.4 Role of NGOs and development partners

Throughout the interviews, the participants outlined the key role that donors, development partners, and NGOs, such as UNICEF, the World Bank, and Chance for Childhood, play in supporting the education of children with SEND in Ghana. For example, participants reported that the World Bank supports the procurement of assistive devices. While the government provides policy frameworks and core funding, the participants indicated that international donors and NGOs frequently supplement these resources, particularly in areas where government budgets are limited. These external actors contribute both financial support and technical expertise, enabling the development of curricula, the provision of assistive devices, and capacity building for teachers. For example, participants described how development partners such as UNICEF fully supported the revision of the national inclusive education policy and continued to support the Ghana Education Service in implementing programmes and activities across schools. Other donors and NGOs contributed through targeted interventions: one organisation funded the development of the Ghanaian Sign Language curriculum, providing both financial resources and expert guidance.

3.5 Donors and NGOs

One individual interview was conducted with a UNICEF representative to gain an understanding of their experiences and the systemic support for learners with SEND in Ghana. The participant provided deep insights into how SEND is conceptualised, prioritised, and supported within the national system. The representative reported that UNICEF views SEND through a social model lens where barriers to learning arise not only from individual difficulties but also from systemic obstacles such as “curriculum rigidity, inaccessible infrastructure, untrained teachers, stigma, and limited data”. The representative outlined that programming prioritises learners with a wide range of disabilities, but also applies an intersectional approach that focuses on learners facing compounded disadvantages such as “girls with disabilities in rural or deprived regions”.

The participant reported that their work aligns with global and national frameworks such as the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, SDG 4, Ghana’s 2015 Inclusive Education Policy, the Education Strategic Plan, the Disability Act, and the Pre-Tertiary Education Act, and

aims to support the government to operationalise their commitments instead of creating parallel systems.

The participant highlighted the organisation's technical and convening roles, including policy advisory support, participation in technical working groups, strengthening teacher capacity, and improving disability-disaggregated data systems. UNICEF also contributes to evidence generation to guide planning and budgeting, bridging the gap between policy aspirations and practical implementation at national and district levels. Sustainability and coordination were emphasised as critical. UNICEF works closely with the Ministry of Education, Ghana Education Service, civil society organisations, and organisations of PWDs to avoid duplication and ensure interventions are embedded within government systems. The participant concluded that the most transformative action would be a nationwide, systematic strengthening of teacher capacity in inclusive pedagogy, supported by reliable data, highlighting teachers as the frontline agents of inclusion.

4. Preliminary recommendations

In line with the desk review, the primary research findings suggest a persistent funding gap, limited awareness and understanding of SEND, limited training opportunities for teachers, limited support services for parents, as well as a gap between policy and implementation, and limited evidence on the effectiveness of adopted SEND initiatives and programmes. Nevertheless, the primary research findings also point to opportunities that, if leveraged, could be developed into effective interventions and practices in the national context, including teachers' collaboration and mentoring schemes and learners' resilience and motivation.

Taken together, the landscape analysis findings show strong motivation and dedication to promote inclusive and equitable quality education for all children in Ghana, reflected both in guiding policies and stakeholders' commitment and engagement in inclusive education discussions. Translating this motivation and commitment into tangible efforts will require a stronger evaluation of current policy implementation and ongoing professional development, ensuring that the inclusion policy translates into effective education practices.

1. Map special schools and inclusive education resource centres to identify resources, services, and gaps for better planning and coordination

Given the limited evidence on the availability of resources and the status of inclusive education in the country, we recommend a comprehensive, up-to-date mapping of all special schools and resource centres. The mapping should capture key information on the geographical distribution of schools, the number and categories of SEND served, and the number, roles, and qualifications of teachers and support staff. It should also assess the quality and adequacy of infrastructure, including accessibility features, the availability of assistive devices, and the suitability of teaching and learning materials.

In addition, the mapping should document progress towards the establishment and functioning of inclusive education resource centres, including the specific services they provide, such as early identification and assessment, teacher professional development, and ongoing support to mainstream schools.

Where possible, the exercise should also gather data on funding sources and include key indicators related to student outcomes, such as retention, progression, and transition rates. This would provide a stronger evidence base to inform planning, resource allocation, and policy development in support of inclusive education.

For this, the Ministry of Education can lead the exercise and maintain a central repository of data after conducting a nationwide survey. While regional and district education offices can provide details regarding resources and facility lists, NGOs can support verification. The mapping will generate key evidence to guide resource allocation, enhance NGO support, enhance coordination of SEND initiatives, and strengthen monitoring of policy implementation.

2. Strengthen monitoring and evaluation of SEND initiatives to generate evidence on effectiveness and inform policy and programme decisions

Establishing a robust monitoring and evaluation system for all SEND programmes and initiatives is recommended. The Ministry of Education can lead the development of a standardised framework and the review of reports, while NGOs and implementing partners can collect and submit impact and process evaluation reports in accordance with the framework. NGOs can also provide financial and technical support for evaluations. This system would allow the government to generate evidence on what works and support scaling of effective programmes.

3. Strengthen policy implementation and funding to ensure effective delivery of inclusive education

The desk review demonstrates that inclusive education is under-resourced. Funding gaps must be systematically identified by the Ministry of Education. Developmental partners and NGOs can supplement funding, provide technical support, implement SEND initiatives, and support capacity building by offering teacher training programmes. The Ministry of Finance should monitor the allocation and use of funds to ensure that all resources are more strategically directed towards SEND-specific resources, school accessibility improvements, teacher training, and inclusive learning technologies. Strengthening coordination and collaboration with NGOs is also essential to ensure efficient use of resources, avoid the duplication of services, and maximise the reach and impact of inclusive education investments.

Further, the Ministry of Education can develop an implementation plan with clear targets, timelines, and responsibilities. Regional and district education offices can ensure that schools follow the plan and report progress.

4. Build teacher capacity to implement inclusive and SEND-responsive teaching practices

Although teachers demonstrated willingness and strong motivation to support the inclusion of children with SEND, the desk review and the primary research findings suggest that existing pre-service and in-service teacher training do not sufficiently prepare teachers to support learners with SEND. The Ministry of Education can review and revise the training curricula to focus on SEND and inclusion. Teacher training colleges and universities can integrate modules into their pre-service programme to support pre-service teachers' theoretical and practical knowledge (e.g., integrating supervised teaching placements, collaborating with circuit supervisors and special educators, introducing case-based learning and simulations). NGOs and development partners can facilitate SEND and inclusion workshops, teacher training programmes, and provide technical support. Thus, providing targeted and continuous professional development to strengthen teachers' capacity for inclusive education is recommended. Further, teachers in this study indicated support for adopting peer mentoring and collaborative approaches. Peer mentoring approaches could be formally integrated into teacher professional development to build communities of practice to strengthen inclusive practices in Ghanaian schools. EdTech tools could be used to promote peer-mentoring schemes, for instance, to facilitate online peer mentoring sessions (e.g., [Bussu & Moran, 2026](#)). Research conducted by [Tripon \(2025\)](#) highlights the importance of an EdTech Mentor Project in building communities of practice and reducing feelings of professional and academic isolation, particularly through collaborative learning environments.

5. Strengthen monitoring, evaluation, and research to ensure data-driven decision-making

Policy and intervention monitoring and evaluation have a significant impact on inclusion outcomes. Thus, developing robust systems to track and evaluate inclusion policy and the implementation of interventions in schools is recommended to ensure accountability, improve the quality of provision, and enhance resource allocation. Although the Education Management Information System (EMIS) provides data for education

management (e.g., student enrollment, number of repeaters, number of teachers), it is considered weak for providing data on some key indicators, such as inclusive and special education ([↑Ministry of Education, no date](#); [↑UNESCO IIEP, 2018](#)). The Ministry of Education can lead the integration of SEND-specific indicators into EMIS, including data on enrolment disaggregated by type of disability and gender, availability of assistive devices, accessibility of school infrastructure, and teacher training in inclusive education. Schools and district education offices can be responsible for regular data collection and reporting.

Additionally, integrating research evidence into policy design is highly recommended to ensure policymaking is informed by proven, high-quality evidence.

6. Enhance access to EdTech to promote inclusive and equitable quality education for all

Research shows EdTech has a significant impact on promoting inclusive education. For this reason, schools should be equipped with accessible EdTech resources. Additionally, collaboration between government agencies, NGOs, and private sector partners is needed to expand reach and maximise the impact of available resources. The Ministry of Education can lead by creating an enabling environment to support the uptake of these initiatives and setting standards for inclusive design. NGOs and development partners can provide technical support, funding, and capacity-building. Key actions should include scaling assistive technologies, ensuring accessibility of digital content, and training teachers in the use of EdTech.

7. Translate willingness into action

Collaboration between government agencies and NGOs is recommended in areas of policy implementation, resource mobilisation, and capacity building. Further, creating systems and communication platforms could be helpful in supporting collaboration between teachers, teachers and parents, and between schools and the government.

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